

Research Article

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OSTRACODS ASSEMBLAGE IN SELECTED AQUATIC BODIES OF MAIDUGURI METROPOLIS AND JERE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS. BORNO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Studies on Ostracods assemblage on selected Aquatic bodies in Maiduguri Metropolis and Jere local government areas of Borno State, Nigeria, were conducted. The monthly and seasonal occurrence of Ostracods species in relation to the following Physico-Chemical parameters: atmospheric temperature, water temperature, transparency, conductivity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), turbidity, nitrate, phosphate, and heavy metals, were studied in various locations and sites, with sites designated as PP (Permanent Pond), NPP (Non-Permanent Pond), SSWW (Semi Static Water, Ways), PSLWB (Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies), NPSLWB (Non-Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies), and W/BFP (Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain), respectively for 12 months., Ostracods occurrence in the various water bodies in Maiduguri and Jere showed four phases separated by anthropogenic impacts, size and type of the water bodies, physical factors, and chemical factors. Variation in occurrence of Ostracods depends on their adaptability and susceptibility to physico-chemical parameters and seasonal changes. Effects of seasons Ostracods of each sites varied monthly as PSLWB and NPSLWB showed higher significance and correlations between Physico-Chemical Parameters and Ostracods compared to PP, NPP, SSWW and W/BFP. A total number of Six (6) Ostracods species confined to one (1) family: Cyprididae were identified. Cypridoidea in Ostracods appeared to be the most dominant taxa. Eucypris virens is the most dominant Ostracods. Sarscypridopsis aculeate is the less dominant Ostracods. Cypridoidea (Ostracods) are not significant and poorly correlated in all sites and Seasons. Ostracods shows significance in the following parameters. ie Water temperature, Depth, Conductivity, DO, Cu, PO₄, Pb, Fe, NO₃, NO₂, and Transparency. The highest value of 0.142 was recorded in nitrates. Moderate level of significance was recorded in water temperature, depth, Fe, PO₄ and transparency with values of 0.332, 0.294, 0.398 and 0.211. Negative correlation, was recorded in atmospheric temperature, TDS, pH, BOD, Zinc, Mn and Cu. The highest non-significance value was recorded in pH, with (-0.453), and the lowest in BOD (-0.058). Moderate non-significance value was recorded in TDS (-0.244), Mn (-0.211). The Physico-Chemical parameters were within the range in unpolluted water bodies of the Tropical arid zone region.

Keywords: Ostracods; Physico-chemical; Sites; Aquatic bodies; Assemblage

INTRODUCTION

The name “Ostracods” comes from a Greek word “Óstrakon” meaning “shell or tile”. They are benthos and detritus feeders, they belong to the phylum “Anthropoda” and a sub-phylum “Crustaceae [1]. Ostracods are small, poorly-segmented entomostracan crustaceans in which the body parts are enclosed within a calcareous bivalve carapace. They occur in almost all aquatic habitats, and ready preservation of their valves in a variety of depositional environment make them an important tool in both palaeoecological and biostratigraphic analysis [2]. The Ostracods are zooplanktons which feed on the phytoplankton and are the second most abundant taxonomic group of zooplankton after copepods. [3] reported that the Ostracods had not received much attention in ecological studies, in spite of their relative high abundance and the vital role they play in nutrient cycling in the aquatic ecosystem. Ostracods are crustacean that are easily recognized by the presence of carapace.

Information on the influence of physico- chemical properties on the species Composition of Ostracods in the arid zone of Nigeria is very scanty in relation to primary and secondary productivity of arid zone water bodies, with respect to strategic management and wise utilization of aquatic resources, importance of Ostracods to ecological studies. Ostracods are very useful for fish as food and for paleoenvironmental and climatic studies, hence the promulgations of holistic approach, that agrees to all ecological Summits and the World Charter for Nature Conservation.

Class Ostracoda is diverse and widespread in the world, but one in which most species are sensitive to the changes in the environmental conditions. Therefore, they can be used bio-indicator to determine water quality, spatial and temporal changes in the environment [4,5].

Anthropogenic activities have been found to be responsible for many acute changes in the water quality parameters of many water bodies including eutrophication due to nutrients drained from agricultural and or municipalities [6].

Ostracods assemblages would be expected only in large stable environment. Certainly, rich faunas featuring a high degree of endemism have been recorded for ancient lakes [7], suggesting fauna of different biogeographic processes at work. The objectives of the study are to determine the seasonal variations in physico-chemical parameters and species composition, and distribution of Ostracods of the aquatic environments and to determine the correlation between the physical and chemical characteristics of water and Ostracods species composition and distributions. Studies on the abundance and ecology of Ostracods is very vital due to the fact that aquatic organisms like other organisms respond to environmental stress in a number of ways but little is known of Ostracods of the study area therefore this will contribute to the knowledge of the limnological biodiversity of the study area.

Study Area

Maiduguri is the capital and the largest city in Borno State, Nigeria which is located on latitude 11⁰ 51' 42''N and longitude 013⁰ 09'' 35E and lies within the northern Sudan Savannah with a distinct dry and wet (rainy) seasons. The town has an annual mean temperature of 37°C.

The town has two (2) main river systems (Ngaddabul and Ngadda Rivers) which met and continues to flow as River Ngadda; both rivers are freshwater bodies which are remarkable for their circular shape. Water from the two (2) rivers is used for irrigation, human consumption, domestic purposes and various industrial activities. Wastes are constantly discharged into the rivers from municipal drainage systems, abattoir, dyeing industries, commercial areas and irrigation Sites along the bank of the rivers. Jere local government area of Borno state has its headquarters in the town of Khaddamari. Jere district comprises of areas such as Addamari, Alau, Bale-Galtimari, Dala-Lawanti, Dusuman, Gongolon-Lawanti Gaboru, Gomari, Koshebe, Maimusari, Mashamari, Masu, Ngudda, Tuba, Fori, Jere, and Mairi.

Figure 1: Map of Maiduguri and Jere showing Sampling Locations

Sampling Sites and Sample Collections

Sampling sites were chosen based on the accessibility, security, populations and activities of the sites. Sampling sites were mapped, and the coordinates marked with (GPS) and six (6) randomly chosen sites taken, considering environmental categories, such as:

1. Permanent ponds of various sizes and depths. Locations, Site (1) Jiddari polo, Maiduguri: GPS 11.79500, 13.14947 Site (2) Usmanti Ward, Maiduguri, GPS 11.85794, 13.21805. Site (3) Gongolon Lawanti Ward, Maiduguri.
2. Non-permanent ponds of various sizes and depth. Locations, Site (1) Beside faculty of Science, University of Maiduguri, GPS 11.81120, 13.20520 Site (2) Kyarimi Park Zoo, Maiduguri, GPS 11.83145 13.14945. Site (3) Chad Basin Development Authority (CBDA), Maiduguri, GPS 11.86096, 13.22024
3. Semi- static water ways and drainage ditches. Locations, Site (1) Abbaganaram Ward, Maiduguri, GPS 11.85849, 13.15609. Site (2) Shehuri Ward, Maiduguri, GPS 11.85349 13.15838 Site (3) Gwange Ward opposite University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH).Maiduguri, GPS 11.82550, 13.17843
4. Permanent small lotic water- bodies. Locations, along River Ngadda, at Site (1) Besides Lagos bridge, Maiduguri, GPS 11.81968, 13.17136 Site (2) Confluence point, between River Ngadda and River Ngaddabul. Site GPS 11.82801 13.15606 (3) Besides Customs Bridge, Maiduguri GPS 11.65174 13.17408
5. Non-permanent small lotic water- bodies. Locations, Site (1) Besides 505 Housing Estates, Maiduguri. GPS 11.85941, 13.21451 Site (2) Shuwari Ward Maiduguri, Site (3) Moduganari Ward, Maiduguri. GPS 11.82423, 13.12744
6. Wells/boreholes flood plains. Locations, Site(1) Mairi Ward, Maiduguri GPS 11.81708, 13.18021 Site(2) Gwange Layin Tanki, Maiduguri, GPS 11.83430, 13.18880 Site(3) Usmanti Ward, Maiduguri, GPS 11.81968 13.17136

Sampling Frequency and Duration of Study

The Sampling was conducted over a period of two years, covering both dry season and wet seasons. Water samples were collected from the sampling sites using duplicate two liters capacity sampling bottles from the six sites, using standard operation procedure (SOP) as described by USEPA [8].

Ostracods Collection, Identification and Counting

Water samples for the Ostracods were collected at each Sampling station using Kick and then grab Sampling techniques. Kick sampling technique involves kicking or stirring a body of water which creates disturbance to the benthos invertebrates, thereby making them to come-up to the surface for easy collection with grab sample collection technique. Ostracods samples were collected from the sediments of each aquatic body using standard pond net (350x350mm wide and 250um mesh size) with handle, fixed with a sampling bottle. It was fixed at site with 70% ethanol, and later on washed, and sieved through standard size sieves. Ostracods was later sorted in the laboratory using binocular microscope, and then identified to the lowest possible taxonomic levels, as described by [9-12].

Determination of Physico-Chemical Parameters and Analysis

Samples of water were placed in acid washed (10% HCl) sterilized bottles for onward transportation to the laboratory of Biological Sciences Department, University of Maiduguri. All glassware was rinsed with 10% HCl, and distilled water before analysis. Water samples are collected in 250mL bottles, and each heavy metal concentration was determined using direct reading spectrophotometer. Conversion factors were applied where necessary as described by [13,14].

Statistical Analysis.

All data on the physical, chemical and biological studies were assessed for normality and homogeneity of variance. Non-normal data was transformed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). When the effects are significant in the ANOVA, Duncan Multiple LSD test was used to distinguished differences between means, ($P < 0.05$). The water quality parameters was be related to the diversity of Ostracods. Diversity index from Margalef information theory [15], and average values from all Sampling aquatic bodies within the year was used.

Atmospheric Temperature

The periodic atmospheric temperature recorded showed a significant difference between parameters and sites (Table 1). The lowest value of 35.58°C was recorded in Permanent Ponds (PP) and the highest value of 36.31°C was recorded in wells/Boreholes flood Plain (W/BFP). There was no significant differences at $P < 0.05$ between Permanent Pond (PP), Non- Permanent Pond (NPP) Permanent-Small lotic Water bodies (PSLWB) and Non-Permanent Small lotic Water Bodies(NPSLWB) and also between Semi- Static Water bodies (SSWB) and Well/ Bore holes flood Plain (W/BFP) (Table 1).

Water Temperature

The highest water temperature of 27.22°C was recorded in in PP, and the lowest temperature of 19.24°C was recorded in SSWW. There were no significant differences at $P < 0.05$ between NPP and SSWW and between NPSLW, and W/BFP. There was a significant difference between PP and the remaining Sites (Table 1)

Depth

The highest mean value of 3.79m was recorded in PSLWB, and the lowest mean value of 0.56m was recorded for W/BFP. There was no significant difference of $P < 0.05$ between NPSLWB and SSWW., while, there was a significant difference between PSLWB and the remaining Sites. (Table 1.)

Conductivity

The highest mean value of 125.30 μcm was recorded in PSLWB, and the lowest value of 108.17 μcm was recorded in W/BFP. There was no significant difference at $P < 0.05$ among the Sites. (Table 1).

RESULTS

Table 1(a): Mean Monthly Summary of the Physico-Chemical Parameters of Sites

	Parameter: Atmospheric temperature											
	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	Jun	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
PP	29.20	28.90	41.10	41.90	41.20	42.20	40.80	38.00	37.00	29.10	29.30	29.30
NPP	28.60	28.80	40.70	43.00	41.70	41.80	42.00	38.60	37.90	29.30	29.20	28.90
SSWW	28.60	28.90	41.00	42.80	41.80	41.90	42.30	39.50	38.80	29.40	29.30	28.90
PSLWB	27.80	28.50	40.20	40.80	40.50	41.30	41.90	39.30	38.70	28.40	29.30	26.50
NPSLWB	28.70	28.90	41.65	42.70	42.40	42.00	42.80	40.00	38.90	29.40	29.40	28.90
W/BFP	28.60	28.80	41.20	42.60	42.10	42.10	42.30	40.30	39.10	29.40	29.20	28.80
Pooled Mean	28.58	28.80	40.98	42.30	41.62	41.88	42.02	39.28	38.40	29.17	29.28	28.55
	Parameter: Water temperature											
PP	22.50	23.50	26.10	27.10	30.20	28.40	28.10	28.30	28.00	29.40	29.60	24.60
NPP	19.10	20.40	21.30	21.40	20.30	20.70	20.70	19.50	19.50	19.80	18.80	18.50
SSWW	19.30	18.90	19.80	21.20	20.10	19.40	19.60	19.03	18.60	18.30	18.20	18.70
PSLWB	22.10	20.80	21.10	21.80	21.60	20.10	20.30	20.10	19.10	20.80	20.10	20.70
NPSLWB	21.90	22.40	24.70	25.70	25.70	24.20	24.60	24.40	23.00	21.50	22.10	21.90
W/BFP	24.10	25.00	25.60	26.80	25.40	24.80	24.70	24.80	24.20	23.80	23.90	23.50
Pooled Mean	21.50	21.83	23.10	24.00	23.88	22.93	23.00	22.69	22.07	22.27	22.12	21.32

Key: PP = Permanent Pond, NPP = Non-Permanent Pond, SSWW= Semi Static Water, Ways, PSLWB = Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, NPSLWB = Non- Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, W/BFP = Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain,

Table 1(b): Mean Monthly Summary of the Physico-Chemical Parameters of Sites

Parameter: Depth (M)												
PP	1.91	2.10	1.90	1.80	1.80	1.90	2.20	2.40	2.60	2.70	2.40	2.10
NPP	2.10	2.20	2.20	2.00	2.00	2.20	2.00	2.20	2.20	2.20	2.20	2.10
SSWW	1.30	1.40	1.40	1.40	1.40	1.40	1.50	1.60	1.70	1.50	1.50	1.40
PSLWB	3.30	3.10	2.70	2.60	2.50	3.20	4.70	5.30	5.60	5.60	4.50	3.90
NPSLWB	0.60	0.70	0.50	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70	1.00	1.30	1.20	1.00	0.80
W/BFP	0.50	0.40	0.30	0.30	0.50	0.60	0.70	0.90	0.90	0.60	0.60	0.60
Pooled Mean	1.62	1.65	1.50	1.42	1.45	1.65	1.970	2.23	2.38	2.30	2.03	1.82
Parameter: Conductivity												
PP	102.50	110.50	120.20	125.03	130.40	142.50	145.20	145.30	150.00	92.40	93.60	100.70
NPP	90.30	108.67	109.57	118.03	119.93	130.37	133.83	133.50	138.50	80.67	82.20	88.73
SSWW	107.25	115.75	124.75	130.30	133.20	145.25	148.55	149.40	153.70	96.05	97.00	102.40
PSLWB	105.20	123.60	124.50	135.00	137.00	144.20	148.50	148.70	149.00	95.50	99.20	104.20
NPSLWB	81.50	99.50	102.60	103.60	112.80	180.30	123.60	125.00	128.60	118.30	108.50	90.50
Pooled Mean	97.35	111.60	116.32	122.39	126.67	148.52	139.94	140.38	143.96	96.58	96.100	97.31
Parameter: TDS Mg/L)												
PP	16.57	21.01	25.67	27.75	30.77	27.03	28.53	29.40	24.10	37.83	34.71	33.72
NPP	13.70	14.37	15.50	17.90	18.77	630.16	20.53	21.30	20.00	18.96	16.63	15.76
SSWW	53.13	54.53	55.92	57.21	59.77	61.66	62.83	66.23	66.73	60.36	57.76	55.96
PSLWB	45.65	48.20	49.58	54.63	56.25	57.80	60.09	62.00	61.70	58.63	55.01	50.27
NPSLWB	18.50	20.15	21.50	23.88	25.41	26.66	27.45	28.56	27.56	26.23	23.16	20.31
Pooled Mean	29.51	31.65	33.63	36.27	38.17	160.66	39.89	41.50	40.02	40.40	37.45	35.20

Key: PP = Permanent Pond, NPP = Non-Permanent Pond, SSWW= Semi Static Water, Ways, PSLWB = Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, NPSLWB = Non- Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, W/BFP = Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain,

Table 1(c): Mean Monthly Summary of the Physico-Chemical Parameters of Sites

PARAMETER: pH												
PP	7.2	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.4	7.43	7.9	8.0	7.9	7.6	7.3
NPP	7.6	7.6	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.6	7.6	8	8.1	7.9	7.6	7.6
SSWW	7.9	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.6	7.8	8	8.3	7.9	7.6	7.4	7.6
PSLWB	7.8	7.4	7.4	7.4	7.5	7.7	7.5	7.9	7.9	7.8	7.7	7.6
NPSLWB	7.8	7.6	7.5	7.4	7.4	7.7	7.5	7.5	7.9	7.9	7.6	7.6
Pooled Mean	7.66	7.48	7.48	7.45	7.5	7.64	7.61	7.92	7.96	7.82	7.58	7.54
PARAMETER: DISSOLVED OXYGEN (DO)												
PP	7.40	8.80	9.70	9.20	10.60	5.70	6.40	8.10	8.80	7.00	7.20	7.50
NPP	2.10	2.10	4.00	3.70	4.60	4.60	4.50	4.70	4.80	3.60	3.30	2.50
SSWW	9.20	11.70	15.50	170	17.30	18.60	22.60	29.60	30.6	21.50	17.80	14.20
PSLWB	2.30	2.70	3.30	3.70	3.60	3.90	4.20	5.70	7.00	6.00	5.00	4.20
NPSLWB	3.00	4.50	4.20	4.80	4.30	4.40	5.00	5.70	6.20	5.20	4.80	4.00
Pooled Mean	4.80	5.96	7.34	7.68	8.08	7.44	8.54	10.76	11.48	8.66	7.62	6.48
PARAMETER: BIOCHEMICAL OXYGEN DEMAND (BOD)												
PP	0.43	0.77	0.40	0.53	0.27	0.73	0.40	0.27	0.50	0.37	0.30	0.43
NPP	0.42	0.43	0.33	0.35	0.35	0.36	0.38	0.41	0.42	0.42	0.4	0.40
SSWW	0.40	0.50	0.51	0.49	0.50	0.52	0.56	0.55	0.54	0.55	0.53	0.49
PSLWB	0.75	0.81	0.79	0.81	0.80	0.79	0.80	0.81	0.81	0.77	0.76	0.76
NPSLWB	0.35	0.46	0.42	0.48	0.43	0.47	0.50	0.54	0.56	0.52	0.51	0.49
W/BFP	0.30	0.31	0.32	0.35	0.36	0.38	0.39	0.41	0.39	0.38	0.36	0.31
Pooled Mean	0.444	0.50	0.47	0.50	0.49	0.50	0.53	0.54	0.54	0.53	0.51	0.49

Key: PP = Permanent Pond, NPP = Non-Permanent Pond, SSWW= Semi Static Water, Ways, PSLWB = Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, NPSLWB = Non- Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, W/BFP = Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain,

Table 1 (d): Mean Monthly Summary of the Physico-Chemical Parameters of Sites

PARAMETER:ZINC (Zn) mg/l												
PP	0.55	0.59	0.59	0.61	0.62	0.62	0.64	0.66	0.67	0.67	0.66	0.63
NPP	0.67	0.72	0.73	0.74	0.7	0.72	0.74	0.76	0.76	0.73	0.71	0.69
SSWW	0.86	0.88	0.89	0.89	0.91	0.93	0.95	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.94
PSLWB	0.49	0.51	0.53	0.53	0.54	0.55	0.56	0.57	0.57	0.56	0.55	0.54
NPSLWB	0.60	0.61	0.62	0.63	0.64	0.65	0.64	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.64	0.64
W/BFP	0.39	0.40	0.42	0.43	0.45	0.46	0.47	0.48	0.49	0.48	0.47	0.46
Pooled Mean	0.59	0.62	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.66	0.67	0.68	0.69	0.68	0.67	0.65
PARAMETER: MANGANSE (Mn) mg/l												
PP	0.35	0.35	0.42	0.43	0.44	0.34	0.32	0.39	0.39	0.39	0.38	0.39
NPP	0.29	0.30	0.30	0.31	0.31	0.32	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.32	0.33	0.31
SSWW	0.70	0.72	0.75	0.75	0.76	0.78	0.79	0.81	0.82	0.83	0.82	0.79
PSLWB	1.24	1.19	1.30	1.32	1.33	1.37	1.36	1.37	1.37	1.36	1.29	1.26
NPSLWB	0.76	0.76	0.77	0.77	0.78	0.79	0.79	0.81	0.82	0.79	0.78	0.77
W/BFP	0.23	0.25	0.26	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.29	0.3	0.27	0.26	0.26
Pooled Mean	0.59	0.60	0.63	0.64	0.65	0.65	0.64	0.67	0.67	0.66	0.64	0.63
PARAMETER: Cu (PPM)												
PP	0.47	0.38	0.48	0.55	0.60	0.47	0.48	0.46	0.43	0.42	0.38	0.39
NPP	0.45	0.47	0.46	0.46	0.47	0.47	0.49	0.50	0.52	0.49	0.48	0.46
SSWW	0.72	0.73	0.74	0.73	0.74	0.74	0.76	0.78	0.79	0.76	0.75	0.73
PSLWB	0.63	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.65	0.67	0.68	0.70	0.71	0.72	0.69	0.67
NPSLWB	0.53	0.54	0.56	0.56	0.57	0.59	0.59	0.55	0.58	0.57	0.53	0.52
W/BFP	0.49	0.50	0.51	0.53	0.54	0.55	0.56	0.58	0.56	0.56	0.55	0.54
Pooled Mean	0.55	0.54	0.57	0.58	0.60	0.58	0.59	0.60	0.60	0.59	0.56	0.55

Key: PP = Permanent Pond, NPP = Non-Permanent Pond, SSWW= Semi Static Water, Ways, PSLWB = Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, NPSLWB = Non- Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, W/BFP = Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain,

Table 1(e): Mean Monthly Summary of the Physico-Chemical Parameters of Sites

PARAMETER: PHOSPHATE (PO ₄) mg/L												
PP	0.43	0.45	0.27	0.27	0.52	0.50	0.51	0.46	0.45	0.42	0.44	0.54
NPP	0.28	0.29	0.30	0.30	0.31	0.33	0.35	0.36	0.35	0.34	0.32	0.31
SSWW	0.35	0.37	0.38	0.39	0.40	0.41	0.42	0.44	0.45	0.45	0.43	0.40
PSLWB	0.51	0.53	0.54	0.53	0.55	0.56	0.57	0.58	0.56	0.56	0.55	0.53
NPSLWB	0.31	0.35	0.36	0.37	0.37	0.38	0.39	0.40	0.41	0.41	0.39	0.37
W/BFP	0.18	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.25	0.26	0.24	0.23	0.20
Pooled Mean	0.34	0.36	0.34	0.35	0.40	0.40	0.41	0.42	0.42	0.40	0.39	0.39
PARAMETER: Pb (ppm)												
PP	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.1	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09
NPP	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.07
SSWW	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.12
PSLWB	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.12
NPSLWB	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.12
W/BFP	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.00
Pooled Mean	0.080	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.09
PARAMETER: Iron (Fe) mg/L												
PP	0.45	0.56	0.45	0.45	0.47	0.52	0.54	0.55	0.55	0.56	0.57	0.52
NPP	0.25	0.25	0.26	0.27	0.28	0.29	0.29	0.30	0.32	0.34	0.36	0.35
SSWW	0.50	0.52	0.53	0.54	0.55	0.57	0.58	0.60	0.61	0.62	0.63	0.60
PSLWB	0.48	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.50	0.51	0.53	0.54	0.57	0.61	0.62	0.59
NPSLWB	0.28	0.29	0.30	0.33	0.34	0.35	0.36	0.39	0.40	0.41	0.39	0.33
W/BFP	0.17	0.18	0.185	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.22	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.19	0.18
Pooled Mean	0.35	0.38	0.37	0.38	0.39	0.40	0.41	0.43	0.44	0.46	0.46	0.43

Key: PP = Permanent Pond, NPP = Non-Permanent Pond, SSWW= Semi Static Water, Ways, PSLWB = Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, NPSLWB = Non- Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, W/BFP = Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain,

Table 1(f): Mean Monthly Summary of the Physico-Chemical Parameters of Sites

PARAMETER: Nitrate (NO ₃)mg/L												
PP	39.90	22.70	40.40	42.50	20.80	20.70	22.5	22.90	22.90	22.50	26.73	26.73
NPP	10.20	10.30	10.40	10.65	10.85	10.70	10.8	10.80	10.40	10.40	10.65	8.795
SSWW	42.55	43.05	43.63	40.58	40.75	40.95	41.6	42.00	42.00	41.75	41.05	40.55
PSLWB	66.05	66.65	67.58	68.00	68.30	69.00	69.8	70.20	69.50	69.50	68.85	67.60
NPSLWB	20.15	20.45	20.80	20.75	20.60	22.15	22.7	23.73	23.22	22.05	20.30	20.20
W/BFP	0.21	0.22	0.23	0.23	0.25	0.71	0.715	0.74	0.23	0.22	0.21	0.20
Pooled Mean	29.84	27.23	30.51	30.45	26.93	27.37	28.02	28.39	28.04	27.74	27.96	27.35
PARAMETER: Nitrate:(NO ₂) mg/L												
PP	36.70	42.50	37.70	38.80	63.30	11.80	11.90	13.80	14.70	40.30	28.90	30.80
NPP	9.70	9.90	9.90	10.00	10.04	10.30	10.60	11.20	11.20	10.70	10.30	9.90
SSWW	30.20	30.80	31.10	30.90	31.50	31.80	32.00	34.10	34.20	33.90	33.10	31.90
PSLWB	70.00	70.20	70.40	70.90	71.10	71.20	71.30	73.60	73.70	72.60	72.30	70.90
NPSLWB	10.80	10.70	10.80	11.00	11.50	12.20	12.40	12.10	11.90	12.10	11.90	11.40
W/BFP	5.10	5.10	5.20	5.30	5.50	5.50	5.60	6.30	6.50	6.30	6.00	5.60
Pooled Mean	27.08	28.20	27.52	27.82	32.16	23.800	23.97	25.18	25.37	29.32	27.08	26.75

Key: PP = Permanent Pond, NPP = Non-Permanent Pond, SSWW= Semi Static Water, Ways, PSLWB = Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, NPSLWB = Non- Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, W/BFP = Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain,

Table 2 shows the mean values of the physico-chemical parameters of sampling sites using Duncan multiple LSD test (DMLT). Results of parameters which include total dissolved solid, transparency, total dissolved solid, Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) mg/L, Zinc (Zn) mg/L, Manganese (Mn) mg/L, Copper (Cu) ppm, Phosphate (PO₄) mg/L, Lead (Pb) ppm, Iron (Fe) mg/L, Nitrite (NO₂) mg/L and Nitrate (NO₃) mg/L are presented and described below

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

The highest value of 59.98 NTU was recorded in NPSLWB, and the lowest value of 17.75 NTU was recorded in NPP. There was no significant difference between SSWW, PSLWB and NPSLWB at P<0.05. There was a significant difference between NPP and the remaining Sites pH.

The highest mean value of 7.74 was recorded in NPP, and the lowest value of 7.44 was recorded in PP. there was no significant difference between all the Sites at P<0.05.

Transparency (cm)

The highest mean value of 29.09cm was recorded in W/BFP, and the lowest value of 16.49cm was recorded in PSLWB. There was no significant difference between SSWW and NPSLWB, and between PP and W/BFP. PSLWB is significantly different compared to the remaining Sites at P< 0.05.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO) mg/L

The highest mean value of 18.77mg/L was recorded in PSLWB, and the lowest value of 3.70mg/L recorded in NPP. There was no significant difference at P<0.05 between NPP, SSWW NPSLWB and W/BFP, while PSLWB is significantly different compared to the remaining Sites.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) mg/L

The highest mean value of 0.78mg/L was recorded in PSLWB, and the lowest value of 0.35mg/l was recorded in W/BFP. There was no significant difference between NPP, PP, NPSLWB and W/BFB, while SSWW and PSLWB are significantly different at P<0.05 compared to the remaining stations.

Zinc (Zn) mg/L

The highest mean value of 0.92mg/l was recorded in SSWW, and the lowest value of 0.45mg/l was recorded in W/BFP. There was a significant difference at P<0.05 between all the Sites.ie PP, NPP, SSWW, PSLWB, NPSLWB and W/BFP.

Manganese (Mn) mg/L

The highest mean value of 1.31mg/L was recorded in PSLWB, and the lowest value of 0.26mg/l was recorded in W/BFP. There was no significant difference at P<0.05 between PP, NPP and W/BFP. There was a significant difference between PSLWB and the remaining Sites (Table 2).

Copper (Cu) ppm

The highest mean value of 0.74ppm was recorded in SSWW, and the lowest value 0.46pp was recorded in PP. there was no significant difference between NPP, NPSLWB and W/BFP, and also between SSWW and PSLWB. There was a significant difference at P<0.05 between PP and the remaining Sites.

Phosphate (PO₄) mg/L

The highest value of 0.54 mg/L was recorded in PSLWB, and the lowest value of 0.2 mg/L was recorded in W/BFP. There was no significant difference between PP, NPP and PSLWB, and between SSWW and NPSLWB. There was a significant difference at P<0.05 between W/BFP and the remaining Sites.

Lead (Pb) ppm

The highest mean value of 0.43ppm was recorded in PP, and the lowest value of 0.02ppm was recorded in W/BFP. There was no significant difference at P<0.05 between all the Sites.

Iron (Fe) mg/L

The highest value of 0.57mg/L was recorded in SSWW, and the lowest value of 0.17mg/L was recorded in W/BFP. There was no significant difference between PP, SSWW and PSLWB, and between NPP and NPSLWB. There was significant difference between W/BFP and the remaining Sites at P<0.05.

Nitrite (NO₂) mg/L

The highest mean value of 11.91mg/L was recorded in NPSLWB, and the lowest value of 5.96 mg/l was recorded in W/BFP. There was no significant difference between PP, PSLWB and NPSLWB, and between NPP, SSWW and W/BFP at P<0.05.

Nitrate (NO₃) mg/L

The highest mean value of 68.41mg/L was recorded in PSLWB, and the lowest value of 0.27mg/L was recorded in W/BFP. There was a significant difference between all the Sites at P<0.05.

Table 2: Mean Values of the Physico-Chemical Parameters of Sampling Sites using Duncan Multiple LSD Test (DMLT)

Parameter	PP	NPP	SSWW	PSLWB	NPSLWB	W/BFP
Water Temp. (°C)	58 ^a	80 ^a	26 ^b	23 ^a	99 ^a	31 ^b
Air temp(°C)	22 ^c	95 ^a	24 ^a	84 ^{ab}	48 ^{abc}	52 ^{abc}
Depth(m)	2 ^b	3 ^b	5 ^b	9 ^c	1 ^a	6 ^a
Conductivity(μ/cm)	1.55 ^a	1.19 ^a	2.96 ^a	5.30 ^b	5.48 ^a	3.17 ^a
Total dissolved solid (TDS)	09 ^b	75 ^a	33 ^c	98 ^c	98 ^c	1 ^{ab}
Transparency(cm)	4 ^a	4 ^b	8 ^b	1 ^b	8 ^a	2 ^a
Dissolved Oxygen DO(mg/L)	99 ^c	25 ^{ab}	09 ^{bc}	49 ^a	39 ^{bc}	09 ^c
Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) (mg/L)	9 ^b	0 ^a	4 ^a	77 ^c	9 ^a	5 ^a
Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) (mg/L)	5 ^a	9 ^a	8 ^b	8 ^b	7 ^a	5 ^a
pH(mg/L)	2 ^c	2 ^d	2 ^d	4 ^b	3 ^c	5 ^a
Ca(mg/L)	8 ^a	1 ^a	7 ^d	1 ^c	0 ^b	6 ^a
Mg(ppm)	6 ^a	7 ^b	4 ^c	7 ^c	5 ^b	4 ^b
Fe(mg/L)	6 ^c	5 ^c	0 ^b	4 ^c	7 ^d	1 ^a
Zn(ppm)	3 ^a	7 ^a	0 ^a	3 ^a	3 ^a	2 ^a
Cu(mg/L)	2 ^c	9 ^d	7 ^c	3 ^c	3 ^d	7 ^a
Mn(mg/L)	45 ^b	6 ^a	5 ^a	16 ^b	91 ^b	6 ^a
Al(mg/L)	28 ^a	52 ^b	74 ^c	41 ^f	54 ^c	7 ^a

Key: PP = Permanent Pond, NPP = Non-Permanent Pond, SSWW= Semi Static Water, Ways, PSLWB = Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, NPSLWB = Non- Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, W/BFP = Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain,

Note: *The mean value with the same superscript on the same rows and column are not significantly different from each other as $p < 0.05$.*

Wet Season

July

The highest mean value of 6.00 was recorded in PP, and the lowest. Value of 4.33 was recorded in SSWW. There was no significant difference at $P < 0.05$ between all the Sites

August

The highest value of 6.00 was recorded in PP, and the lowest value of 4.00 was recorded in NPSLWB. There was no significant difference at $P < 0.05$ between all the Sites.

September

The highest value of 6.33 was recorded in PP, and the lowest value of 3.67 was recorded in NPP. There was no significant difference between SSWW, PSLWB, NPSLWB and W/BFP. The Site PP is significantly different at $P < 0.05$ compared to the remaining Sites.

October

The highest mean value of 6.67 was recorded in PP, and the lowest value of 4.33 was recorded in NPP and NPSLWB. There was no significant difference between NPP, SSWW, PSLWB, NPSLWB and W/BFP. The Site PP is significantly different at $P < 0.05$ compared to the remaining Sites.

Dry Season

November

The highest mean value of 6.67 was recorded in PP, and the lowest value of 4.33 was recorded in SSWW and W/BFP. There was no significant difference at $P < 0.05$ between all the Sites.

December

The highest mean value of 5.50 was recorded at PSLWB, and the lowest value of 4.67 was recorded in NPP and NPSLWB. There was no significant difference at $P, 0.05$ between all the Sites.

In terms of Ostracods specie occurrence and distributions in relation to Physico-chemical parameters, the results shows that the relationship is non-significant in the month of January, February, March, and April with values of 0.875, 0.964, 0.693 and 0.110 at $P < 0.05$. It becomes significant in the month of May, June with values of 0.001, 0.048 when $P < 0.05$. Then non-significant in the month of July with value of 0.724 when $P > 0.05$. The remaining month of August, September, October and November are significant with values of 0.036, 0.018, 0.012, 0.041 when $P < 0.05$ and becomes non-significant in December with values of 0.977 when $P > 0.05$.

Table 3: Mean Monthly Summary of the Variation in the Number of Occurrences of Ostracods According to Sites

es	N	B	AR	R	AY	N	L	IG	P	T	V	C
	3 ^a	3 ^a	7 ^a	0 ^b	3 ^b	7 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	3 ^b	7 ^b	7 ^a	3 ^a
P	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	7 ^{ab}	7 ^a	3 ^a	7 ^a	7 ^a	7 ^a	3 ^a	7 ^a	7 ^a
WW	3 ^a	0 ^a	3 ^a	0 ^{ab}	7 ^a	0 ^a	3 ^a	3 ^a	7 ^{ab}	7 ^{ab}	3 ^a	0 ^a
LWB	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^{ab}	0 ^{ab}	0 ^a	0 ^a
SLWB	0 ^a	0 ^a	3 ^a	3 ^{ab}	7 ^a	3 ^a	7 ^a	0 ^a	7 ^{ab}	3 ^a	0 ^a	7 ^a

Key: PP = Permanent Pond, NPP = Non-Permanent Pond, SSWW= Semi Static Water, Ways, PSLWB = Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, NPSLWB = Non- Permanent Small Lotic Water Bodies, W/BFP = Wells/Boreholes Flood Plain

Note: The mean value with the same superscript on the same rows and column are not significantly different from each other as $p < 0.05$

The results shows significance in the following parameters. ie Water temperature, Depth, Conductivity, DO, Cu, PO₄, Pb, Fe, NO₃, NO₂, and Transparency. The highest value of 0.429 was recorded in Pb which indicates higher level of significance and lowest value of 0.142 was recorded in nitrates. Moderate level of significance was recorded in Water temperature, Depth, Fe, PO₄ and Transparency with values of 0.332, 0.294, 0.398 and 0.211 respectively.

In terms of negative correlation, it was recorded in Atmospheric temperature, TDS, pH, BOD, Zinc, Mn and Cu. The highest non-significance value was recorded in pH, with (-0.453), and the lowest in BOD (-0.058). Moderate non-significance value was recorded in TDS (-0.244), Mn (-0.211)

Table 4: Pearson Correlations (R) between Physico-Chemical Parameters with Ostracods

Physico-Chemical Parameters	Ostracods	Significance	Sample Size (n)
Temp	0.05	NS	43
Temp	0.159	S	193
pH	0.294	S	252
Conductivity	0.179	S	493
S	0.244	S	346
r	0.453	S	68
D	0.183	S	483
D	0.058	S	824
c	0.53	S	809
	0.211	S	416
	0.184	S	479
	0.225	S	386
	0.429	S	86
	0.398	S	114
b ₃	0.142	S	587
b ₂	0.312	S	223
Transparency	0.211	S	250

KEY:

S= Significant NS= Not-Significant

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2 tailed)

Discussions

The study has revealed that the Ostracods community and the Physico-Chemical constituents of water bodies in Maiduguri varied with Months, locations, Sites and Seasons. The thermal factor showed considerable fluctuations. The low temperatures recorded from October to February were due to the Harmattan and the North east dry winds. In early May, June and July, the rains and the associated Cloudy weather caused the decrease in temperature. [16,17] noted that climatic factors were the determining factors for water temperatures. [18], suggested that Climatic factors were the determining factors for increase and decrease in temperature of the Arid Zone, Particularly Maiduguri Metropolitan, shares climate of the north east arid zone. The water temperature in this Study falls within the normal temperature range (25^o-35^oC) of natural tropical waters [19]. The adequate life in the tropics is adapted to these changes [20]. This also agrees [21] which agrees that temperature affects both Ostracods and Phytoplanktons in various location and Sites (Table 4).

Additionally, water bodies exhibit spatial distributions of Phytoplanktons reflecting both biological and physical properties. The results also agrees with [22] that indicates Ostracods population density and diversity varies Spatio-temporal and depending on a range of environmental factors such as water temperature. It also agrees with [23], that Sites prone to drying during some months of the year is most likely going to have lower Ostracods levels. Ostracods is positively correlated to water temperature and negatively correlated to Atmospheric temperature

Depth is an inevitable factor in any aquatic ecosystems as stratification plays a great role in physiology, adaptation and distributions. The highest depth level of 3.79m was recorded in PSLWB, and the lowest depth level of 0.56m was recorded in W/BFP. The depth level across the Sampling Sites varies within the year, across seasons. The depth of the Sites tends

to increase during the Wet Seasons (Table 4). The result of the study shows positive correlations with Ostracods. The result also shows that Ostracods are positively correlated to depth. (Table 4).

The Conductivity value of 125.30 μcm was recorded as the highest in NPSLWB, and the lowest value of 108.17 μcm was recorded in W/BFP with no significant difference among all the Sampling Sites (Table 4.). The specific conductance of the water bodies was less than 600 μcm recorded from Kiri Reservoir [24]. The maximum value of 125.30 μcm recorded is an indication of oligotrophy. It implies low level of Dissolved salts, a characteristic feature of “soft water.” The low level may be associated with bedrock of the water bodies, which is known to be poor in salt regeneration. This goes to explain that increase in conductivity every month, and the highest during the rains was as a result of dissolved salts brought in by floods, and ostracods abundance as both are positively correlated with conductivity (Table 4.). The result of the study agrees with [25-28].

The Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) recorded in the water bodies Started increasing during the Wet Seasons, from May-October and low in the dry Seasons (harmattan) Table 4. The high value of TDS during the rains has been due to flooding, which brought in high concentration of sediments into the water bodies. The increase in TDS could influence turbidity, and therefore light penetration for primary production, and affects feeding by biotic communities relying on Sites. The Sites SSWW, PSLWB and NPSLW were more sediment laden than PP, NPP and W/BFP. This could be as a result of organic matter that were introduced from other sources as both SSWW and PSLW are semi-static, and static water ways. [19] suggested that excessive concentration of TDS might be harmful to aquatic life. The harmful effect may be the killing or reduction of their growth rate as well as reduction of food available to the fauna. The non- correlation with Ostracods may be due to negativity to light and their benthic life styles.

The Sampling Sites are shown to be neutral. The highest value of 7.74 was recorded in NPP, and the lowest value of 7.44 was recorded in PP. there was no significant difference between all the Sampling Sites, throughout the year and seasons (Table 4). This agrees with [30] that photosynthesis and respiratory processes determine to a large extent the hydrogen ion concentration in an aquatic ecosystem. [17,31,32] noted that in African waters, alkaline conditions are not typical. It agrees with [33] that decay of allochthonous and autochthonous organic materials in the water bodies would decrease the pH to below 7.0. the nature of the basement granite-biotite must be important in the buffering of the water pH to above 7.8. The results of this work indicate pH is negatively correlated to Ostracods. (Table 4.) and hence linked to an increase in phytoplankton occurrence with associated increase in their photosynthetic actions would deplete the free- carbon dioxide leading to an increase in pH levels.

Water transparency varies from 16.49cm to 29.09cm in all the Sampling Sites. This is very low compared to 0.45-2.8m in lentic water bodies like lake Kainji [28]. The progressive decrease in water transparency from October has no relationship with increased Ostracods abundance. The remarkable decrease from May to October after the onset of the Wet Season indicated that floods draining into the various water bodies were responsible for the low transparency within that period, rather than Ostracods production.

Biswas [34] observed that in lake Volta, Ghana. Secchi disc transparency decreased with increase in Phytoplankton. Olaniyan [35] suggested that transparency varies directly with rainfall in freshwater bodies, and it determines the depth of which light essential for photosynthesis can penetrate. This study revealed that water transparency is positively correlated with Ostracods, which disagrees with [34], may be due to the combination of heterogeneous water bodies, both lotic and lentic, in which the research was conducted (Table 4).

The patterns of DO vary between Sites. It ranges 3.70mg/L (NPP) to 18.77mg/L (PSLWB). DO levels in the Sites sampled proved to be insignificant. There was no significant difference between all the Sites (Table 4). The relative level of dissolved oxygen in June may have been due to the decomposition process of Organic matter brought into the water bodies through surface run-offs. The relatively higher values from March to May were due to the high photosynthetic activities, as well as reduced decaying process. It has been noted in this work is slightly positively correlated (0.183) with Ostracods.

This disagrees with [34, 36,37]. Duchene [38] consider that whereas wind is a major oxygenator in lakes, dissolved oxygen in smaller lakes and other lentic water bodies is determined by photosynthetic action of Phytoplanktons, not Ostracods, as shown in Table 4.9 in NPP and NPSLWB, DO level, and Variation in Ostracods (Table 4) (NPP). Complete oxygen depletion was not observed in any Sites of the location, apparently because of non-lentic nature of the water bodies, and the prevailing winds of the north-east arid zone. This agrees with [39] that asserted that DO was the most critical variable in water. The amount available in water depends on the presence of Phytoplanktons, time of the day, turbulence of water body, water temperature and the amount of water discharged into the water. Also Helfrich *et al.* [40] said that the Solubility and dynamics of oxygen distribution in water bodies are basis to the understanding of aquatic ecosystems. It also indicates potential of primary productivity. The result of this work indicates lower levels of primary productivity which agrees with [40].

The Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) exhibited the same trend as dissolved oxygen. It ranges from 0.35mg/L (W/BFP) to 0.78mg/L (PSLWB). The lowest value in W/BFP is not surprising as it is unstable in nature because of small surface area and higher in PP because of an increased depth and size, which agrees with [39]. The BOD values were high in September and lower in October. There was no significant variation between the values recorded in all Sites. The higher values recorded in PSLWB could probably be due to Organic matter degradation, which utilize oxygen, which agrees with [41,42] that said Organic matter decomposition from increased human activities can increase the BOD Variation.

The Concentration of Manganese showed considerable variation among the Sites. The highest level was recorded in PSLWB (1.3mg/L) and the lowest in W/BFP (0.26mg/L), the highest level of contamination in various Sites could be associated with the domestic washing with soaps, effects of fertilizers, herbicides and pesticides from the neighboring households. Odiete [43] reported that domestic sewage and agricultural effluents has the capacity to precipitate Manganese salts, which may exact toxic effects on aquatic organisms. Other sources may be as a result of localized inputs and sediments transport. The highest level of 1,3mg/L in PSLWB is higher than the acceptable limits of 0.10mg/L by [44]. This may be due to implicated land-based urban sediment transport, as well as individual sources, which agrees with [45]. The result of this study shows negative correlation between Manganese and Ostracods, and slight correlation between Manganese and agrees with the reports of [31,46].

The Copper concentration recorded is lower than 0.95mg/l recorded in Arizona desert reservoir [47], but it higher compared to the permissible pollution limits of 0.10mg/l recommended by [44]. The significant increase in copper concentration in all Sites, may be linked to the activities occurring, such as excessive land run-offs into the water, and hence affinity with Copper sulphate, which is basic components of pesticides and insecticides used in nearby communities. It is also linked to the activities, such as run-offs from mechanical workshops directly into the water. On the contrary the value of Copper was higher in the dry season than in Wet Season. Wright *et al.* [48] reported that the concentration of Fe, Cu, and Mg were higher during the Wet Season than in dry seasons. The result reported in this work indicates strong negative correlation between copper and Ostracods.

The Monthly variation of phosphate-phosphorous in the Sites varied between 0.45mg/L, 0.40mg/L, 0.54mg/L, 0.37mg/L and 0.21mg/L, with PSLWB recording the highest and W/BFP recording the lowest. The pattern of phosphate-phosphorous fluctuations was not in line with the temperature regimes and phytoplankton maximum phosphate concentration was obtained from June to August corresponding to the time of high run- offs. There was a subsequent decrease from September as the rains progresses, possibly due to dilution effects. There was a marked depletion from November to January. This agrees with [49] that 68% of phosphate was from run-offs and only 28% from other sources. The phosphate- phosphorous value range recorded in this study falls below the observed ranged of 3.8-6.30mg/l, which disagrees by the observation of [30] in some African rivers, lakes, and water bodies. The result of the study shows a positive correlation to phosphate-phosphorous by Ostracods (Table 4), which agrees with [50], that observed that phosphorous is the most important and limiting substances controlling organic production.

The highest concentration of lead (0.43ppm) was recorded in PP, and the lowest concentration of 0.02ppm was recorded in W/BFP. The concentration of lead across the Sampling Sites falls among the acceptable limits. The result of the work shows positive correlations with Ostracods, which agrees with Francis *et al.* [51].

The iron concentration in all the Sites is relatively low. The highest value was recorded in PSLWB (0.53mg/L), and the lowest value in W/BFP (0.17mg/L). The lowest value recorded in W/BFP may be connected to the source of the water supply, mostly motorized bore-holes. The concentration of iron is consistent with the low solubility of iron desert reservoirs, and arid-zones as reported by [47]. The concentration of iron in the aquatic bodies may be due to direct or indirect discharge from metal dump Sites in and around the Sites. The concentration of Iron (Fe) was higher in Harmattan season than in Wet Seasons. Entry of the heavy metals into the aquatic bodies, especially during the Wet Season may be through the floods, and this tends to increase the concentration of the metals during the rains. The result agrees with the findings of Amuzu *et al.* [52] that heavy metals occur in low concentrations in aquatic ecosystems. The values accrued from all the Sites were lower than the values suggested by WHO (2000) for drinking water. Hart [53] classified as surface water with 1.9mg/L of iron as slightly polluted, 2.7mg/L as polluted, and above 2.7mg/L as heavily polluted. On the basis of Harts classification, all the water bodies can be classified as unpolluted. It was also found out that iron concentrations are highly correlated to Ostracods.

The seasonal variation of nitrate- nitrogen followed well known and predictive pattern, but in the case of various water bodies sampled, it disagrees with the predictive pattern of [54]. The lowest value of 0.27mg/L was recorded in W/BFP, and the highest value of 68.41 was recorded in PSLWB, with significant difference between all the Sites. Relatively nitrate-nitrogen was low in the sampled water bodies compared to 238-300mg/L in lake Asejire, [55,56], lake Kariba (0-200mg/L) [56] and lake Victoria (5-11mg/L).

The nitrate-nitrogen level as found in this research work is very much lower than the values reported by [57], while working on Shen reservoir in Plateau State, Nigeria. He recorded a range of 59-30-87ppm. The amount of nitrate-nitrogen in a body of water at any one time is depended on a dynamic relationship between a number of factors, such as the amount which is dissolved out of the soil, over which the water enters the reservoir and flows [56]. The rate of regeneration from the bottom deposits and dead organic matter, and the rate of utilization by Phytoplanktons [35].

Nwoko [58] had suggested that the nitrate-nitrogen could get into the water through various sources. Such as cattle dungs, fertilizer run-offs, and leaching of leguminous farms. It was also confirmed from this study that both Ostracods are correlated to nitrate nitrogen (Table 4).

This study shows that metal concentration in the aquatic water bodies is not high. The variation in the concentration of heavy metals in the water may be mostly attributed to the discharge of dumped waste, domestic activities, agricultural activities, as well as direct washing of dry and wet particles by harmattan winds and flood.

Within the study period of two years covering dry season and wet season, quantitative and qualitative changes occurred among the physico-chemical parameters, Ostracods in various locations and Sites.

Conclusion

Ostracods and physico- chemical variables in the sampling sites of various locations were shown to be affected by Sites, locations and Seasons through their general and specific properties. Ostracods occurrence in the various water bodies in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council (MMC) and Jere local government area showed four phases separated by anthropogenic impacts, size and type of the water bodies, Physical factors, and Chemical Factors. Variation in occurrence of Ostracods depends on their adaptability and susceptibility to Physico-Chemical Parameters and Seasonal changes. Temperature, nitrate, phosphate, transparency, depth and turbidity appeared to be of overriding importance to occurrence and distribution of Ostracods in various location and sites. Effects of seasons on Ostracods of each sites varied monthly. PSLWB and NPSLWB showed higher significance and correlations between Physico-Chemical Parameters with Ostracods compared to PP, NPP, SSWW and W/BFP. Six (6) Ostracods species confined to one (1) family: *Cyprididae* were also identified.

Chlorophyceae (Phytoplankton) and *Cypridoidea* (Ostracods) appeared to be *Eucypris virens* is the most dominant Ostracods. *Sarscypridopsis aculeate* is the less dominant Ostracods. *Chrysophyceae* . *Cypridoidea* (Ostracods) are not significant and poorly correlated in all sites and Seasons.

The physico-chemical parameters were within the range in unpolluted water. Variation may be due to effect of agricultural activities through fertilizer application, herbicides, pesticides, and other pollutants.

In order to uphold the UN charter that all species and habitats should be safeguarded to the extent that is technically, economically, ecologically and politically feasible. The following are recommended.

Communities in the arid zone region like Maiduguri should be encourage adopting environmentally friendly initiative by embracing low and Non-waste technologies (LNWT).

Monitoring of the Aquatic bodies should be encouraged as part of environmental management policy, so as to control the effluents that enters the aquatic bodies, and hence maintains acceptable limits of metal concentrations, such as lead which is hazardous to human and aquatic life. With the identification of Ostracods in the aquatic bodies. More research work need to be conducted on the link between Ostracods, Physico-chemical parameters and aero-edaphic-hydro complex in the arid zone region of Nigeria, in order to bring out ecological index for holistic approach.

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